

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****THE NUTRITIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SELENIUM,
COBALT AND MAGNESIUM, AND THE EFFECTS OF ITS
DEFICIENCY ON ANIMAL HEALTH****Habib ur Rehman^{1*}, Mohammad Din², Niamatullah Kakar³ and Ahmad Khan Tareen³**¹ Department of Microbiology, Univesrity of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan² Livestock and Dairy Development Department, Ziarat. Balochistan.³ Institute of Biochemistry, University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Microelements such as selenium and cobalt and macroelement as magnesium are indispensable nutrients for preserving major physiological functions, improving reproductive characteristics and overall health condition. By their adequate use, the different diseases are prevented, while at the same time they have a positive effect on fertility and resistance. Insufficient quantities of these micro and macro elements, inadequate the absorption and interaction with other elements, lead to the impairment of the immune response due to metabolic and oxidative stress. In the recent study, the better biological availability of micro and macro elements improve the quality of products and optimize the digestive quantities of food in animals with maximizing the immune function and protection of tissues. For example Selenium (Se) is a micro nutrient essential in very small quantities. The requirement for selenium by ruminants is approximately 0.1 to 0.3 ppm. The metabolic role of selenium is as a component of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase. This enzyme is found inside the body cells and is responsible for detoxifying peroxides. Selenium is also required for the normal development of the pancreas. The initial deficiency of dietary selenium in cattle is recognized as the cause of "White Muscle Disease" in calves, damaging to cell membrane and tissue membranes. The deficiencies in dietary selenium and vitamin E result in increased incidence of mastitis. Selenium deficiency is one of the numerous factors causing Retained placenta. The Retained placenta has adverse economic effects as it leads to develop uterine infections which increase the incidence of infertility. Blind staggers or alkali disease is the most common problem associated with selenium toxicity. Cobalt (Co) is necessary in ruminant feed for the production of vitamin B12. Cobalt may also be advantageous in ruminant feed as a source of refining the proficiency of fiber digestion by bacteria. Although cobalt requirements are less than 1 ppm in the feed, ruminal synthesis of B12 is radically augmented within hours of cobalt supplementation of a poor diet. Cobalt deficiency has disturbing properties on animal health. Its deficiency leads to anemia, fatty liver, increased mortality of offspring shortly after birth, increased vulnerability to infectious agents and infertility. Cobalt deficiency may directly affect the metabolism of rumen bacteria which in turn affect the digestion process. Feeding well-fortified trace mineralized salt comprising cobalt is the best source of insuring that animals get satisfactory cobalt nutrition. Cobalt supplementation above that required by the animal, increase the volatile fatty acid concentrations in the rumen fluid, leads to improve the rate of fiber digestion. Magnesium (Mg) is traditionally classified among the macro-mineral elements. Magnesium plays a role in maintaining constant physical chemical properties of cells, in ionized form, it regulates calcium and potassium cytosol flow, which is especially important in muscle and cardiac tissue integrity, transfer of nerve impulses and muscle contraction. The main concentration of magnesium in the body is in the skeleton, which contains 60-70% of the total. Magnesium works by modifying enzyme activity and by concentrating rumen fermentation on acetic and butyric acid, at the expense of propionic acid. Hypomagnesium, grass tetany, winter tetany, or infantile tetany is a metabolic condition found in dairy cows at the start of lactation, caused by a sudden fall in magnesium concentration in the cerebro-spinal fluid and in blood leads to a state of neuromuscular excitability with convulsive-type nervous signs. It is often accompanied by hypocalcaemia. Specific magnesium supplementation before and during risk periods can compensate for the fall in feed magnesium digestibility. In this review paper, an investigation has been recognized to inspect the effects of minerals supplement in single and/or joined form on animal health and their negative effects of deficiency in different species of animals.

Corresponding author:**Habib ur Rehman,**

Department of Microbiology,

Univesrity of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan

* E-mail: ur_2085qta@yahoo.com, Cell No. +92 0332-2955166

Please cite this article in *press* Habib ur Rehman et al., *The Nutritional Significance Of Selenium, Cobalt And Magnesium, And The Effects Of Its Deficiency On Animal Health.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Mineral matters such as selenium, cobalt and magnesium are indispensable nutrients for preserving major physiological functions, improving reproductive characteristics and overall health state. These micro and macro elements play an important role in synthesis of proteins, vitamin metabolism, forming of connective tissue, fertility (Rabiee et al., 2010), weight gain (Enjalbert et al., 2006) and in preserving/improvement of immune function of animals. Proper supply of these minerals have a beneficial effect on health, fertility, lactation and immune functions (Griffiths et al., 2007). By their adequate utilizes different ailments are prevented, while at the same time they have a positive effect on fertility and resistance. Insufficient quantities of these microelements, inadequate absorption and interaction with other microelements may lead to the impairment of the immune response due to metabolic and oxidative stress (Sordillo, 2011). Moreover, significant fall in these mineral level may due to several interactions between mineral matters in digestive tract of ruminants.

Role of selenium, Cobalt and Magnesium in preserving the Health Status, Production Processes and Reproduction Performance

1. Selenium: Selenium (Se) is an essential trace element and key food ingredient exerting multiple actions related to animal production, fertility, disease prevention and providing oxidative protection to the organism. Its biological role is performed through the enzyme glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px). The activity of this enzyme depends on the level of selenium in food, that can be used as a reliable indicator of biological uptake of selenium. On the basis of differences in metabolic pathway and competency of action, the organic selenium in the form of selenomethionine and inorganic selenium in the form of Na-selenate or Na-selenite are used in animal nutrition. High levels of inorganic selenium are more toxic than the same levels of organic selenium (Joksimović Todorović et al., 2006; Joksimović Todorović and Davidović, 2014). In recent years, mainly organic forms of micro and macroelements have been administered to animals' results in showing the

better biological availability and having retention time more and longer in the organism. In addition, organic forms improve quality of products for human nutrition (Bozena et al., 2017).

Selenium (Se) was first identified in the early 1800s but its nutritional importance has only been recognized in the later half of this century. Selenium is a micro nutrient element essential in very small quantities. The requirement for selenium by ruminants is approximately 0.1 to 0.3 ppm. In the past, there was controversy over whether selenium was an essential nutrient or a toxic element. In the early 1930s, selenium was identified as the toxic agent causing lameness and death in livestock grazing certain range plants. It was almost 25 years later when selenium was first identified as an essential nutrient. The importance of Selenium in animal physiology was first reported in 1957, when its deficiency was associated with that of vitamin E, which resulted in White muscle disease (WMD) or Nutritional muscular dystrophy (NMD) due to white streaks in the striated muscle, with degenerative changes in skeletal muscle and in the myocardium of young animals (Gabryszuk and Klewicz, 2002, Muth et al., 1958). WMD causes new born mortality, especially in ruminants, and impaired production condition in growing and adult animals. However, its biological significance as a structural part of "selenoenzymes" was understood until 1973 with the discovery of glutathione peroxidase (GSH-PX) and its role in the regulation of oxidative processes and cell membrane protection (Rotruck et al., 1973). In the same year, Se was reported as being a structural component of bacterial reductases (Stadtman, 2005). Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-PX) enzyme was the first proven selenoenzyme that can prevent oxidative damage of the cellular membrane. Actually more than 30 selenoenzymes have been described, most of which are involved in enzyme activity and metabolic regulation of oxidative processes, in animal or bacterial cells and in a hierarchy process for expression in the animal. More than 80% of protein-bound Selenium is selenocysteine. Currently at least 4 GSH-PXs have been recognized (Allan et al., 1999). A Se deficiency prevents the synthesis and function of

GSH-PXs, which protect against peroxides generated in the intermediary metabolism of the cells with the oxidation of fats and proteins of the membranes. Thus, Se deficiency especially damages cellular and mitochondrial membranes (Combs and Combs, 1986; Behne and Kyriakopoulos, 2001).

The main role of selenium in body metabolism is as a component of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase. Glutathione peroxidase is an enzyme found inside body cells and is responsible for detoxifying peroxides. Peroxides are "high energy" oxygen-containing molecules that are produced during the metabolism of fat. These peroxides can be very destructive to body cells and tissues if not captured and detoxified by glutathione peroxidase. Selenium is also a component of other enzymes and is required for the normal development of the pancreas. Vitamin E and selenium are closely linked and are both involved in a variety of metabolic processes. Both nutrients are required to protect tissue membranes from damage arising from the end products of oxidative processes. Selenium, as a part of glutathione peroxidase, acts within (inside) the cells to capture and destroy peroxides before they can compromise the integrity of the cell membranes. Vitamin E is located within the cell membrane and acts as a free radical scavenger. Therefore, vitamin E acts to reduce the spread of damage to cell membrane once it occurs. Because selenium and vitamin E work together to reduce damage to cell membranes, selenium and vitamin E can partially replace one another. If adequate levels of selenium are available to detoxify peroxides before they can cause damage, then less vitamin E is necessary to repair or stop damage. Conversely, if inadequate selenium is available, then more vitamin E is needed to prevent damage caused by the peroxides that do not get detoxified by glutathione peroxidase. However, neither selenium nor vitamin E can fully replace the other. Tissue selenium and glutathione peroxidase concentrations may be used as indicators of selenium status (Enjalbert *et al.*, 2006).

Selenium is known for its physiological effects like antioxidant, antimutagenic and anticarcinogenic properties, it also acts against microbes as well as parasites and has anti-inflammatory effects, engages in metabolism, growth and development, protects organs from oxidative stress, affects immune function and improves fertility. Selenium has become one of the most widely recognized nutrient deficiencies in the U.S. USDA scientists estimate that beef, dairy and sheep producers lose \$545 million yearly due to selenium deficiency (Tyler *et al.*, 2003). Selenium was recognized as a

potentially toxic mineral many years before it was identified as an essential nutrient. It was not until 1957 that the role of selenium in preventing liver necrosis in the rat and exudative diathesis in chicks was recognized. Selenium is required for a good immune response. It is present in all cells of the body, but the concentration is normally less than 1 ppm. Selenium availability of ruminants varies from 11 to 35% while for nonruminants it is from 77 to 85% of oral Selenium. The site of absorption of the element in both cases is the duodenum (Groff *et al.*, 1995). Toxic concentrations in liver and kidney are normally between 5 and 10 ppm (Church and Pond., 1989). Diverse forms of Se supplements are available, but many factors affect their activity and efficacy, such as its chemical form and animal's health and production condition. Selenium status in soil, plants and animal blood and tissue can be used in the diagnosis of Se deficiency (Bozena *et al.*, 2017).

Selenium is critical to thyroid hormone synthesis and the relationship of Se with thyroid activity is further describing by the role of thyroid peroxidase, a selenoenzyme, in the process of iodization of globulin, avoiding thyroid epithelial cell membranal damage (Gärtner *et al.*, 2007; Schomburg *et al.*, 2007). Deiodinases of peripheral tissues are also selenoenzymes, which are very necessary for the activation of T3 (active form) from T4 (thyroxin inactive form) (Beckett *et al.*, 1993, 2005). These relationships between Se and thyroid function, explain the negative effects of Se deficiency in animal production (John *et al.*, 2003). The application of Selenium as an immune system stimulant has a positive impact on the immune response and quality of the colostrum (Jendryczko, 1994). Neutrophils from Se supplemented cows show greater phagocytic and bactericidal activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, and increase the production of leukotrienes (Grasso *et al.*, 1990). The production and activity of the chemotactic factors and migration of white blood cells is reduced in Se deprived animals (Aziz and Klesius, 1985; Jukola *et al.*, 1996) Selenium deficiency affects blood levels of IgG and T cell function, and this determines a higher prevalence and severity of different diseases in animal populations (Muhammad *et al.*, 2013).

The testicles and seminal material shows high concentration of Selenium, mainly associated to the GPX4. The GPX4 deficiency determines low seminal fertility in animals and human, with low sperm counts and increased abnormalities, evident from the sperm development. The effect of Se on female fertility and litter size has given contradictory results; some authors have reported

positive effects with supplementation (Segerson and Ganapathy, 1980; Sheppard *et al.*, 1984), while others did not observe significant effects (Gabryszak and Klewicz, 2002). The conflicting results of Se supplementation on fertility and productivity could depend on the severity of the deficiency, the conditions of supplementation, and the apparent ability of the system to prioritize the enzymatic synthesis under these conditions.

Selenium is part of the active sites of enzymes by becoming a selenocysteine (Driscoll and Copeland, 2003; Stadtman, 2005; Beckett and Arthur, 2005; Köhrle *et al.*, 2007). The ability to catalyse processes of oxidoreduction is associated with the increased capacity of ionization of selenol at physiological pH, on thiol groups (sulphur) of cysteine. Replacing selenocysteine by cysteine dramatically reduces the oxidoreductive ability of selenoenzymes (Driscoll and Copeland, 2003). However, in microorganisms and plants, where Se is also associated with protein fractions, selenomethionine is the most abundant selenoamino acid. Methylselenocysteine is the largest selenified compound in selenium accumulating plants, and it is also present in roots of plants such as garlic and onions (Whanger, 2002; Bozena *et al.*, 2017).

The application of antioxidants in dairy cows reduces the duration and intensity of disease. Antioxidative status of selenium is one of the factors which impacts the reproduction of dairy cows. Selenium has the capability to reduce the occurrence of postpartum ailments in dairy cows such as retained placenta, mastitis, metritis, endometritis, ovarian cysts and leads to increase the level of conception. The application of antioxidants in dairy cows reduces the duration and intensity of disease. Precise mechanisms into the improvement of health of mammary gland are not completely known but they are associated with their antioxidative functions (Joksimović Todorović and Davidović, 2007b; Joksimović Todorović *et al.*, 2012). Antioxidants in dairy cows increase the resistance to mastitis, provide phagocytic capacity of neutrophils increasing the chemotaxis at the spot of the infection (Spears and Weiss, 2008). Inadequate protection against free radicals or high levels of superoxide may lead to the reduction of neutrophil granulocytes that may have the incidence of a disease as a consequence. A primary function of selenium is to increase the migration of neutrophil granulocytes and to provide immunological defense into inflammatory region where they will ingest and destroy present bacteria. Selenium deficit leads to a functional disorder of all the cells of the immune system. The activity of T lymphocytes and NK cells (killer

cells) is decreased along with the low synthesis of some antibodies (Sordillo, 2005). Addition of antioxidants in optimal quantities in food are adopted for dairy cows with the aim of maximizing immune function and protection of tissues (Bozena *et al.*, 2017).

Placenta retention is a disease with a multifactorial etiology, one of which may be a selenium deficiency. The state in which placenta is retained for more than 12h is considered as having a disease. Numerous factors, including mechanical, nutritive and infective causative agents can impact the incidence of this disease. Incidence of placenta retention is often (about 50% animals) associated with zoonoses, such as brucellosis, salmonellosis, leptospirosis and listeriosis (Gunay *et al.*, 2011). One of the studies indicated that placenta retention is one of the major causes of endometritis in cows (Han and Kim, 2005). Retained placenta have adverse economic effects because over half of the animals affected develop uterine infections which increase the incidence of infertility, deficit the percentage of conception, complicate conception or prolong the calving interval (Bella and Roberts, 2007). Injections of selenium during the dry period have been shown to reduce the incidence of retained placenta.

During a transitory period the physiological stress, metabolic, hormonal and biochemical changes occur when they prepare for parturition. A prepartum function of neutrophils decreases that can provoke the occurrence of postpartum diseases. Selenium improves the function of neutrophils, influences their migration and chemotactic activity. An increased concentration of cortisol represents a response to stress and inflammation of pregnant uterus. Cortisol can diminish the function of neutrophils or completely prevent their activity and provoke this disease. The increased content of cytotoxic aldehyde (malondialdehyde) in erythrocytes and increased concentration of cortisol are considered as major causes of the onset of this disease. Many studies indicate that adequate levels of selenium, many other minerals and certain vitamins, which play a role of antioxidants, can decrease the percent of individuals with retained placenta disease. (Tillard *et al.*, 2008; Sharma *et al.*, 2011; Joksimović Todorović and Davidović, 2007a, 2013).

The significant metabolic changes can occur due to the nutrient needs of mammary gland necessary for the synthesis of milk. Simultaneously there occurs reduced uptake of food, negative energy balance (Roche *et al.*, 2009) and oxidative stress (Sordillo and Aitken, 2009). The infections of mammary gland and uterus are frequent in dairy cows during peripartum period. Other health disorders which

may happen in that period are milk fever and ketosis. There is significant connection between the incidence in cows with milk fever, the clinical mastitis occurs five times more frequently compared to the cows which have no such health problems (Curtis et al., 1985). Dairy cows are exposed to numerous genetic, physiological and external factors which can endanger the immunity and increase the frequency of the incidence of mastitis (Sordillo, 2011).

Bicalho et al. (2007) and Formigoni et al. (2011) established that supplementing the mineral matters to dairy cows can lead to decrease in the number of stillborn calves and the incidence of endometritis which is important for preserving proper reproductive performances. The study by Machado et al. (2012) showed that systemic addition of microelements to dairy cows' feeds can significantly reduce the number of cows with intra-uterine contamination by *Fusobacterium spp.* and *Trueperella spp.* These bacteria are associated with the disease of uterus, particularly the onset of metritis and clinical endometritis.

Consequences of Selenium Deficiency: The Selenium deficiency seriously affected the productive efficiency and animal health, with high mortality in the offspring as a result of degenerative lesions in the myocardium and muscular dystrophy in adults (Ramírez et al., 2005). Among the effects of Se deficiency on productive efficiency are lower weight gains (Oblitas et al., 2000), lower milk and wool production, reduced fertility and litter size (Sheppard et al., 1984) and low seminal quality (Beckett and Arthur, 2005). The lowest activity of GSH-PX results in direct damage from peroxides on cell membranes, especially mitochondrial. It also increases the erythrocyte fragility consistent with anaemia, and damage to the endothelium membrane resulting in general oedema. Damage to membrane structures is originally recognized by Se deficiency as a health problem, such as white muscle disease (WMD) or nutritional muscular dystrophy (MND), with degenerative changes in skeletal muscle and in the myocardium of young animals (Spears et al., 1986; Gabryszuk and Klewicz, 2002).

Consequences of Selenium Toxicity: Selenium toxicity is associated with high selenium levels in soil. Soils containing greater than 0.5 ppm of selenium are potentially dangerous to livestock. A few species of plants, such as *Astragalus* (milk vetch), *Macaerantha* (woody aster), *Haplopappus* (goldenweed), and *Stanleya* (Prince's plume) are known to be selenium accumulators. These plants can be very toxic to grazing animals because they

may accumulate selenium at levels greater than 1,000 ppm. Blind staggers or alkali disease is the most common problem associated with selenium toxicity. Symptoms include emaciation, loss of hair, soreness and sloughing of the hooves, excessive salivation, blindness, and death. Restricting access to potentially toxic forage and feeding diets high in protein and sulfur to slow selenium absorption are the most practical means of preventing selenium toxicity. Most of the time for livestock producers, selenium deficiency is a much greater concern than selenium toxicity (Xia et al., 2005).

2. Cobalt: Cobalt (Co) is recognized as a necessary in ruminant feed for the manufacturing of vitamin B₁₂. Cobalt in the form of vitamin B₁₂, which helps to produce red blood cells (used as a treatment for anemia) and maintain the body's nervous system. In recent times, results of numerous current studies suggested that cobalt is beneficial in ruminant diets as a means of improving the efficiency of fiber digestion by bacteria. Although cobalt requirements are less than 1 ppm in the diet, cobalt deficiency has devastating effects on animal health. Feeding a well fortified trace mineralized salt containing cobalt is the best means of insuring that animals get adequate cobalt nutrition. The optimum source of cobalt for livestock are forages grown on cobalt-rich soils (Griffiths et al., 2007).

Ruminants show response to cobalt supplementation and monogastric animals show no response was a unidentified for several years. This mystery was resolved when the cobalt was recognized with 4.4% of the molecular weight of vitamin B₁₂ and that rumen bacteria leads to synthesize B₁₂ efficiently, these differences started to make logic. Cobalt deficiency in ruminants in actual indirectly leads to a vitamin B₁₂ deficiency which committed with cobalt supplementation. Because monogastric animals do not have a bacterial population in the gut that can synthesize sufficient vitamin B₁₂, cobalt supplementation is ineffective. Monogastric animals must have vitamin B₁₂ in their diet or practice coprophagy to prevent a deficiency. In wild species, ingestion of feces is common among monogastric animals. Many of the vitamins B including B₁₂ are manufactured as a consequence of bacterial fermentation in the large intestine, but B₁₂ is expelled out because it must be bound by an intrinsic factor formed in the stomach before it can be absorbed. Coprophagy is one source of gaining the vitamins B that are lack in the basal diet. Clear evidence of a cobalt requirement independent of the B₁₂ requirement has not been documented in monogastric animals. Ruminant feces are an excellent source of vitamin B₁₂. In the 1930s, it was

observed that feeding pigs and cattle together in the same pen improved the health and performance of the pigs, if they were not fed animal proteins. Now it is known that pigs on plant-based diets were deficient in vitamin B₁₂. When cattle and pigs were in the same pen, the pigs pick up enough B₁₂ from the cattle feces to prevent the deficiency (Rabiee *et al.*, 2010).

Synthesis of vitamin B₁₂ by rumen or other bacteria is incredible, as it is one of the most complex non-polymeric natural products produced in nature. Ruminant production of B₁₂ is dramatically enlarged within hours of cobalt supplementation of a deficient diet. Suttle *et al.* (1989) reported that ruminal B₁₂ synthesis increased quadratically, being proportional to the square root of the dose between 1 and 32 mg of cobalt per head in sheep. A 10 mg dose ensured in approximately three times greater B₁₂ synthesis than a 1 mg dose. In general high forage diets and high levels of intake favor B₁₂ synthesis in ruminants.

The recent Irish research suggested that the metabolism of rumen bacteria may directly be affected by the cobalt deficiency which in turn may affect the digestion process. Kennedy *et al.* (1991) reported large increases in succinate concentration in rumen fluid within two weeks after sheep were fed with cobalt deficient barley based diet. They suggested that propionate producing bacteria like *Selenomonas ruminantium* may be especially susceptible to a cobalt deficiency. In 1996 (Kennedy *et al.*) reported that succinate concentrations increased within two days after being fed a diet containing 0.02 ppm cobalt, except on feed having 0.04 ppm cobalt. Florida researchers also reported rapid changes in the rumen microbial population of animals grazing cobalt deficient forages (Gall *et al.*, 1949).

The cobalt supplementation above that the required amount for B₁₂ synthesis may improve the consumption of poor quality forages. The rate of fiber digestion in the rumen is a key factor affecting voluntary intake on high forage diets. Supplementation of cobalt above animal requirements may increase the capability of bacteria to digest fiber. Divalent cations such as cobalt may allow bacteria to associate with plant cell walls. The cellulose enzymes formed by bacteria are retained on the cell membrane and are not released into the environment. Consequently, the bacteria must physically attach to the fiber particle for the enzymes to digest the cellulose. It determines that when a negatively charged bacterium has difficulty attaching to a negatively charged fiber particle, cobalt with two positive charges can serve as a means of linking the two

surfaces (Lopez-Guisa and Satter, 1992). In one experiment, cobalt increased the rate of *in situ* corn fiber digestion from 3.4 to 6.2% per hour. In other experiments cobalt supplementation above that required by the animal increased volatile fatty acid concentrations in the rumen fluid (John *et al.*, 2005), suggesting that the rate of fiber digestion was upgraded. Forages containing less than 0.07 ppm cobalt require supplementation (Underwood and Suttle, 1999). Inorganic sources of cobalt must be soluble in the rumen to allow bacteria to incorporate cobalt into vitamin B₁₂. Cobalt oxide has lower nutritive value than equal amounts of cobalt from more soluble means such as cobalt carbonate or cobalt sulfate (Ammerman *et al.*, 1982; NTP, 2016).

In cobalt deficient ruminants, the rapid loss of appetite is not approximately as noticeable in vitamin B₁₂ deficient monogastric animals. Monogastric energy metabolism is based on glucose absorbed from the small intestine, while ruminants get approximately 70% of their metabolizable energy from volatile fatty acids produced in the rumen. Acetate, propionate and butyrate are the main volatile fatty acids consumed for energy. Normal propionate metabolism needs vitamin B₁₂. Accumulation of propionate in the blood rapidly weakens the appetite (Farningham and Whyte, 1993), and there is an inverse relationship between feed intake and propionate clearance in cobalt-deficient sheep (NRC, 1984 & 1985).

Consequences of Cobalt Deficiency: There is a steady loss of appetite, weight loss, muscle wasting, depressed appetite, anemia, and eventually death when ruminants are on a cobalt deficient diet for a long time (Underwood and Suttle, 1999). The animals appear as if they have been starved, except that the visible mucus membranes are blanched and the skin is pale and fragile. Secondary signs of a cobalt deficiency include fatty liver, increased mortality of offspring shortly after birth, increased susceptibility to infectious agents and infertility (NTP, 2016). Australian researchers associated cobalt with coast disease of sheep and wasting disease of cattle at earliest of 1935.

Cobalt Toxicity: Cobalt has a relatively low order of toxicity in all animals. Cobalt toxicity in ruminants is rare because toxic levels are about 300 times requirement levels. However, acute contact with high levels of cobalt by breathing in humans and animals consequences in respiratory effects, such as a significant decrease in ventilatory function, congestion, edema, and hemorrhage of the lung (ATSDR, 1992; Zywiell *et al.*, 2016). However, excesses need to be avoided.

Table. Liver B12 as Indicator of Cobalt Status

B12 in Fresh Liver (ppm)	Cobalt Status of Animal
Less than 0.07	Severe cobalt deficiency
0.07-0.11	Moderate cobalt deficiency
0.11-0.19	Mild cobalt deficiency
0.19 or more	Sufficiency

Table provides information that indicates the cobalt status in ruminants as determined by vitamin B12 levels in the liver (Miller., 1979).

Table. Cobalt Requirement and Toxic Levels

Class of Animal	Cobalt Requirement in Total Diet (ppm)	Toxic Level in Total Diet (ppm)
Dairy Cattle	0.1	10
Beef Cattle	0.1 (0.07-0.11)	10
Sheep	0.1-0.2	10 ²
Goats	0.1-0.2	10 ³

Table gives data on the requirements for cobalt by the various classes of animals. It also gives the maximum tolerable level of cobalt as established by the National Research Council (NRC, 1984, 1985 and 1989).

3. Magnesium: Magnesium (Mg) is an essential nutrient for all animals, serving a variety of vital functions within the body. Magnesium in the body is mainly present in the skeleton, containing 60-70% of the total. Magnesium is a mineral that is required by all animals and functions as an enzyme cofactor. It is very important to the central nervous system because it competes with calcium in the excitation secretion coupling process. Despite being present at low levels, magnesium is traditionally classified among the macro mineral elements. Magnesium plays a role in maintaining constant physical and chemical properties of cells, in ionised form, it regulates calcium and potassium cytosol flow, which is especially important in muscle and cardiac tissue integrity, transfer of nerve impulses and muscle contraction. In dairy cattle, magnesium also helps raise the butter fat content of the milk and neutralizes acidosis caused by high amounts of grain in their diet. Magnesium is also important in converting sugars into energy (Underwood and Suttle, 2010; Skřivan *et al*, 2016). Magnesium supplementation remarkably improves the digestibility of feed. In cows and sows, it has improved the reproduction and shortened the service period. In beef animals it increased the weight gain and enhanced the milk production in dairy animals. In addition, increasing Mg intake benefits the quality of newborn and improves progeny yield. However, increasing Mg intake has not altered visceral composition of embryos, although brain and liver might have the capacity to store Mg at intake above the requirement (Katalin *et al.*, 2004; Ismail and Ismail, 2016).

The forage is low in magnesium, sodium and soluble carbohydrates, but high in nitrogen,

potassium, and higher fatty acids. Feeding high levels of potassium generally has depressed blood serum magnesium in ruminants (Fontenot, 1979) as a result of reduced magnesium absorption (Newton *et al.*, 1972). The main effect of potassium is on preintestinal magnesium absorption. Tomas and Potter (1976) reported that magnesium infused into the omasum or abomasum was completely recovered at the duodenum, but 36% to 61% of magnesium infused into the rumen was not recovered at the duodenum. Correspondingly, it has been shown that ruminal infusion of potassium in sheep resulted in a large decrease in magnesium absorption, but infusing potassium into the abomasum or ileum had no effect. Magnesium is transported across the ruminal mucosa by an active sodium-linked process (Fontenot, 1979). In fact, Marten and Rayssiguier (1980) suggested that dietary or salivary sodium deficiency decreases the sodium:potassium ratio in rumen fluid, which results in depressed magnesium absorption. They reported a fourfold increase in magnesium absorption when the sodium:potassium ratio in rumen fluid increased from 0.5 to 5.0 (Kaye & Laby, 2014).

Incorporating magnesium in cereal-rich feed reduces the lowering effect of these diets on fat levels and increases fat content in low-fat cows' milk. Magnesium works by modifying enzyme activity and by concentrating rumen fermentation on acetic and butyric acid, at the expense of propionic acid by the buffering effect of magnesium. Magnesium assists in the utilization of calcium and potassium, and functions in enzyme reactions to produce energy. Magnesium protects the lining of arteries and helps form bones. It helps

prevent cardiovascular disease, osteoporosis, and some cancers. By acting with vitamin B₆, magnesium can help prevent or dissolve calcium oxalate kidney stones, the most common kind of stones. Dietary magnesium deficiency is uncommon, but may occur in chronic alcoholics, persons taking diuretic drugs, and as a result of severe, prolonged diarrhea (Grace, 1983; Coursey et al., 2016).

Marten et al. (1987) reported that magnesium absorption in sheep increased from 22.3% to 34.5% when 2.3 grams sodium were added to a low-sodium, dried grass diet. The ruminal sodium:potassium ratio in this study increased from 0.9 to 5.5. These data suggest that inadequate salt supplementation may increase the susceptibility of animals to grass tetany. Swerczek (2003) also observed that cattle with access to loose salt rarely have grass tetany. Certainly when there is a marginal magnesium deficiency, increasing the sodium:potassium ratio in the rumen fluid may be critical to maximizing the absorption of the magnesium that is available.

Magnesium is important to all farm animals. Dairy scientists are investigating the use of magnesium oxide as one means of raising milk butterfat levels in cows fed high concentrate diets. High concentrate diets depress the fat level in milk. Therefore, magnesium supplementation, which at first was used only for beef cattle, is now used with dairy cattle, horses, sheep and other animals. Many horse scientists now recommend the addition of 5% magnesium oxide to salt for horses to protect against a possible magnesium deficiency (NRC, 1989). An adequate and continuous supply of dietary magnesium is needed to prevent magnesium tetany, since animals have limited capacities to store and mobilize magnesium (Haynes, 2015). More studies are needed on magnesium availability in feeds and the factors that affect it.

Compounds used as supplemental magnesium sources include magnesium in the form of oxide, hydroxide, carbonate, sulfate, chloride, or as dolomite. Magnesium oxide contains the highest concentration of magnesium and has been used most commonly to prevent grass tetany. Preventing the risk of grass tetany depends as much on breeding and feeding practices as it performs on agricultural strategy aiming to increase magnesium concentration in feed. Specific magnesium supplementation before and during risk periods may compensate for the fall in feed magnesium digestibility (Bhandari et al., 2016).

Consequences of Magnesium Deficiency:

Hypomagnesium, or grass tetany is a metabolic condition found in dairy cows at the start of lactation or when ruminants are put out to pasture in the spring. The condition is caused by a sudden fall in magnesium concentration in the cerebrospinal fluid and thus in the blood. Symptoms include a state of neuromuscular excitability with convulsive type nervous signs. It is often accompanied by hypocalcaemia. There are several kinds of hypomagnesium: grass tetany, winter tetany, infantile tetany, etc. Contributory factors include: dairy cows over 5 years of age, young grass based feed, climatic conditions and nitrogen fertilizers. Furthermore, the presence of elements in the diet (organic and long fatty acids, sulphates, manganese, aluminium, calcium, sodium and potassium) can in itself, or at high levels reduce magnesium absorption. Consumption of sodium and magnesium simultaneously may be critical to increasing magnesium absorption (Coursey et al., 2016).

Magnesium Toxicity: Magnesium has a rare chances of toxicity in animals. The increased magnesium intake are not common, because the kidney is able to eliminate excess magnesium from the body by rapidly reducing its tubular reabsorption to almost negligible amounts (Haynes, 2015).

Table. Summary of trace minerals function and consequences of their Insufficiency

Mineral	Trace Mineral Function	Trace Mineral Insufficiency
Selenium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Essential Component of Glutathione Peroxidase •In metabolism of Thyroid hormone •Immune response •prevent liver necrosis in rat •Prevent exudative diathesis in chicks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cramping of Muscle •Reduced stress tolerance •Impaired immunity •Subpar performance •Postpartum ailments
Cobalt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For synthesis of Vitamin B₁₂ required by ruminants by bacteria in the gut •Bacterial needs for fiber fermentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Decrease Vitamin B12 levels •Deprived Growth •Decrease body condition
Magnesium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Enzyme co-factor/ Speed up chemical reactions •Extensively involve in the metabolism of fats, carbohydrates and proteins, and transfer energy •Involve in regulating blood pressure, blood sugar, muscle movement, nerve function and immune system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Tetany, Muscle weakness •Nerve and Heart problems •High blood pressure, •Mental disturbances •Depression and seizures •Impaired immunity

CONCLUSION:

Trace elements are essential for health, growth, production and reproduction. They are essential for functioning of a number of components of the immune system. Thus, they contribute to maintaining proper health and immunity. They are important for functioning of a number of enzymes and proteins which are involved in many physiological and biochemical processes. These physio-biochemical processes are linked to growth, production and reproduction. Hence trace element affects both the health and production performance of animals.

Adequate trace mineral intake and absorption is the fundamental requirement for a variety of metabolic functions including immune response to pathogenic challenge, reproduction and growth. As animal trace mineral status declines immunity and enzyme functions are compromised first, followed by a reduction in maximum growth and fertility, and finally normal growth and fertility decrease prior to evidence of clinical deficiency. In order to maintain animals in adequate trace mineral status, balanced intake and absorption are necessary.

The application of organic form of mineral matters in the nutrition of dairy cows during pregnancy and lactation period has a positive effect on immune system and on overall health status. Moreover, their application reduces the percentage of animals with postpartum diseases (placenta retention, mastitis, metritis, endometritis) improving their reproductive performances.

REFERENCES.

1. Allan, C.B., Lacourciere, G.M and Stadtman, T.C., 1999. Responsiveness of selenoproteins to dietary selenium. *Ann. Nutr.* 19, 1–16.
2. Ammerman, C.B., Henry P.R and Loggins, P.R., 1982. Cobalt bioavailability in sheep. *J of ani Sciences*, 55(1):403.
3. ATSDR, 1992. Toxicological Profile for Cobalt. Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. Public Health Service, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Atlanta.
4. Aziz, E.S., Klesius, P.H., 1985. The effect of selenium deficiency in goats on lymphocyte production of leukocyte migration inhibitory factor. *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 10, 381–390.
5. Beckett, G.J., Nicol, F., Rae, P.W., Beach, S., Guo, Y., Arthur, J.R., 1993. Effects of combined iodine and selenium deficiency on thyroid hormone metabolism in rats. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr. Suppl.* 57, 2405–2435.
6. Beckett, G.J., Arthur, J.R., 2005. Selenium and endocrine systems. *J. Endocrinol.* 184, 455–465.
7. Behne, D., Kyriakopoulos, A., 2001. Mammalian selenium-containing proteins. *Annu. Rev. Nutr.* 21, 453–473.
8. Bella, M.J., Roberts, D.J., 2007. The impact of uterine infection on a dairy cows performance. *Theriogenology*, 68 (7), 1074-1079.
9. Bhandari, B. M., Ajay, G., Garg, M.R and Saikat S., 2016. Study on minerals status of dairy cows and their supplementation through area specific mineral mixture in the state of Jharkhand. *J. Ani. Sci & Technology*, 58(42), 2-8.
10. Bicalho, R.C., Galvao, K.N., Cheong, S.H., Gilbert, R.O., Warnick, L.D., Guard, C.L., 2007. Effect of stillbirths on dam survival and reproduction performance in Holstein dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 90, 2797–2803.
11. Bozena, H., Marta, K., Sylvie, S., Carlos, F., Branislav, R.N., Thembinkosi, D.M., Jiri, S., Mojmir, B., Magdalena, M., Jarmila, Z., and Rene K., 2017. A Summary of New Findings

- on the Biological Effects of Selenium in Selected Animal Species. A Critical Review. *Int. J. Mol. Sci*, 18(10), 2209.
12. Church, D.C., and Pond, W.G.. 1989. *Basic Animal Nutrition and Feeding*. 3rd edition. John Wiley and Sons, New York.
 13. Combs, G.F., and Combs, S.B., 1986. *The Role of Selenium in Nutrition*. Academic Press, New York, Chap. 11, 463–525.
 14. Coursey, J.S., Schwab, D.J., Tsai, J.J and Dragoset, R.A., 2016. Atomic Weights and Isotopic Compositions (version 4.1), National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg.
 15. Curtis, C.R., Erb, H.N., Sniffen, C.J., Smith, R.D., Kronfeld, D.S., 1985. Path analysis of dry period nutrition, postpartum metabolic and reproductive disorders, and mastitis in Holstein cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 68, 2347-2360.
 16. Driscoll, D.M., and Copeland, P.R., 2003. Mechanism and regulation of selenoprotein synthesis. *Ann. Rev. Nutr*, 23, 17–40.
 17. Enjalbert, F., Lebreton, P., Salat, O., 2006. Effects of copper, zinc and selenium status on performance and health in commercial dairy and beef herds. Respective study. *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition*, 90, 459- 466.
 18. Farningham, D. A., and Whyte, C.C., 1993. The role of propionate and acetate in the control of food intake in sheep. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 70, 37-46.
 19. Fontenot, J.P., 1979. Animal nutrition aspects of grass tetany. In V.V. Rendig and D.L. Grunes (Ed.) *Grass Tetany*. Am. Soc. Agron. Special Public. No. 35, Madison, WI.
 20. Formigoni, A., Fustini, M., Archetti, L., Emanuele, S., Sniffen, C., and Biagi, G., 2011. Effects of an organic source of copper, manganese and zinc on dairy cattle productive performance, health status and fertility. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 164, 191–198.
 21. Gabryszuk, M., and Klewicz, J., 2002. Effect of injecting 2-and 3-year-old ewes with selenium & selenium-vitamin-E on reproduction and rearing of lambs. *Small Rumin. Research*, 43, 127-132.
 22. Gall, L.S., Burroughs, W., Gerlaugh, P., and Edgington, B.H., 1949. Bacteria Counting Technique. *J. Animal. Science*, 8, 431-441.
 23. Gärtner, R., Gasnier, B., Dietrich, J., Krebs, B., and Angstwurm, M., 2007. Selenium supplementation in patients with autoimmune thyroiditis decreases thyroid peroxidase antibodies concentrations. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metabolism*, 87, 1687–1691.
 24. Grace, N.D., 1983. The site of absorption of magnesium in ruminants. In: J.P. Fontenot, G.E. Bunce, K.E. Webb, Jr. and V.G. Allen (Ed.) *Role of Magnesium in Animal Nutrition*. Virginia Poly. Inst. and State Univ., Blacksburg.
 25. Grasso, P.J., Scholz, R.W., Erskine, R.J., Eberhart, R.J., 1990. Phagocytosis, bactericidal activity and oxidative metabolism of milk neutrophils from dairy cows fed selenium supplemented and selenium deficient diet. *Am. J. Vet. Res.* 51, 269–272.
 26. Griffiths, L.M., Loeffler, S.H., Socha, M.T., Tomlinson, D.J., Johnson, A.B., 2007. Effects of supplementing complexed zinc, manganese, copper and cobalt on lactation and reproductive performance of intensively grazed lactating dairy cattle on the South Island of New Zealand. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 137, 69–83.
 27. Groff, J.L., Gropper, S.S., Hunt, S.M., 1995. *Microminerals*. In: *Advanced Nutrition and Human Metabolism*, West Publishing Company, Minneapolis, 381–384.
 28. Gunay, A., Gunay, U., Orman, A., 2011. Effects of retained placenta on the fertility in treated dairy cows. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*, 17(1), 126-131.
 29. Han, Y. K., Kim, I.H., 2005. Risk factors for retained placenta and the effect of retained placenta on the occurrence of postpartum diseases and subsequent reproductive performance in dairy cows. *J. Vet. Sci*, 6, 53-59.
 30. Haynes, W. M ., 2015. *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*, CRC Press/Taylor and Francis, Boca Raton, FL, 95th Edition.
 31. Jendryczko, A., 1994. Modulatory properties of selenium in immune processes. *Wiadomosci Lekarskie*, 47, 198–202.
 32. John, R., Arthur, Roderic, C., McKenzie, Geoffrey, J., Beckett, 2003. Selenium in the immune system. *J. Nutrition*, 133, 1457–1459.
 33. John, D., Donaldson, Detmar, B., 2005. Cobalt and Cobalt Compounds. *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH.
 34. Joksimović tođorović, M., Jokić, Ź., Hristov, S., 2006. The effect of different levels of organic selenium on body mass, bodyweight gain, feed conversion and selenium concentration in some gilts tissues. *Acta Veterinaria*, 56, (5-6), 489-495.
 35. Joksimović tođorović, M., Davidović, V., 2007a. Selen i vitamin E – reproduktivni poremećaji kod mlečnih krava. *Veterinarski glasnik*, 61, 1-2, 3-10.
 36. Joksimović tođorović, M., Davidović, V., 2007b. Selenium, oxidative stress. III Symposium of Livestock Production with International Participation, Proceedings, 527-

- 530.
37. Joksimović tođorović, M., Davidović, V., Relić, R., 2012. Oxidative stress-mastitis. Proceedings of the first International Symposium on Animal Science, Belgrade, Serbia, Book 2, 673-680.
 38. Joksimović tođorović, M., Davidović, V., 2013. The effect of antioxidants on preventing the retained placenta in dairy cows. *Biotechnology in Animal Husbandry*, 29, 4, 581-589.
 39. Joksimović tođorović, M., Davidović, V., 2014. Effects of inorganic and organic selenium supplementation on blood and milk selenium concentration in dairy cows. Proceedings of The International Symposium on Animal Science, Belgrade-Zemun, Serbia, 543-550.
 40. Ismail, A.A., and Ismail, N.A., 2016. Magnesium: A Mineral Essential for Health Yet Generally Underestimated or Even Ignored. *J. Nutr. Food. Sci*, 6, 523.
 41. Jukola, E., Hakkarainen, J., Soloniemi, H., Sankari, S., 1996. Blood selenium, vitamin E, vitamin A, and B-carotene concentrations and udder health, fertility treatment and fertility. *J. Dairy Sci.* 76, 838-845.
 42. Katalin, K.G., Orsolya, S, László,G., and Petronella S., 2004. Magnesium in Animal Nutrition. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 23(6), 1-8.
 43. Kaye and Laby, 2014. Tables of Physical & Chemical Constants, 16th edition.
 44. Kennedy, D.G., Young, P.B., McCaughey,W.J., Kennedy, S., and Blanchflower,W.J., 1991. Rumen succinate production may ameliorate the effects of cobalt-vitamin B₁₂ deficiency on methymalonyl CoA mutase in sheep. *J. of Nutrition*. 121:1236.
 45. Kennedy, D.G., Kennedy, S., and Young, P.S., 1996. Effects of low concentrations of dietary cobalt on rumen succinate concentrations in sheep. *International J. for Vitamin and Nutri Research*, 66:86.
 46. Köhrle, J., Jakob, F., Contempré, B., Dumont, J.E., 2007. Selenium: The thyroid and the endocrine system. *Endocr. Review*, 26, 944-984.
 47. Lopez-Guisa, J.M., Satter, L.D., 1992. Effect of copper and cobalt addition on digestion and growth in heifers fed diets containing alfalfa silage or corn crop residues. *J. Dairy Science*. 75(1):247-56.
 48. Machado, V.S., Oikonomou, G., Bicalho, M.L., Knauer, W.A., Gilbert, R., Bicalho, R.C., 2012. Investigation of postpartum dairy cows' uterine microbial diversity using metagenomic pyrosequencing of the 16S rRNA gene. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 159, 460-469.
 49. Marten, H.N., and Rayssiguier, Y., 1980. Magnesium metabolism and hypomagnesemia. In Y. Ruckebusch and P. Thivend (Ed.) *Digestive Physiology and Metabolism in Ruminants*. pp 447-466. AVI Publishing Co. Westport, CT.
 50. Miller, W.J., 1979. *Dairy Cattle Feeding and Nutrition*. Academic Press, Inc. New York.
 51. Muhammad, I.Y., Archana, S., Padinjare, M. D., Biju-Peer, H., Sarita, D., Ranbir, S. J., and Umesh, D., 2013. Role of trace elements in animals: a review. *Veterinary World*, 6(12): 963-967.
 52. Muth, O.H., Oldfield, J.E., Remmert, L.F., Schubert, J.R., 1958. Effects of selenium and vitamin-E on white muscle disease. *Science*, 128, 1090.
 53. Newton, G.L., Fontenot,F.P., Tucker,R.E., and Polan,C.E., 1972. Effects of high dietary potassium intake on the metabolism of magnesium by sheep. *J. Anim. Science*, 35, 440.
 54. NRC, 1984. *Nutrient requirement of beef cattle*. National Academy Press. Washington.
 55. NRC, 1985. *Nutrient requirements of sheep*. National Academy Press. Washington.
 56. NRC, 1989. *Nutrient requirements of dairy cattle*. National Academy Press. Washington.
 57. NRC, 1989. *Nutrient requirements of horses*. National Academy Press. Washington.
 58. NTP, 2016. *Cobalt and cobalt compounds that release cobalt ions in Vivo*. National Toxicology Program. Department of Health and Human Services, USA.
 59. Oblitas, F., Contreras, P.A., Böhmwald, H., Wittwer, F., 2000. Efecto de la suplementación con selenio sobre la actividad sanguínea de glutation peroxidasa (GSH-PX) y ganancia de peso en bovinos selenio deficientes mantenidos a pastoreo. *Arch. Vet. Medicine*, 32, 55-62.
 60. Rabiee, A.R., Lean, I.J., Stevenson, M.A., Socha, M.T., 2010. Effects of feeding organic trace minerals on milk production and reproductive performance in lactating dairy cows: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 93, 4239-4251.
 61. Ramírez, B.E., Tórtora, J.L., Huerta, M., Hernández, L.M., López, R., Crosby, M., 2005. Effect of selenium-vitamin E injection in selenium-deficient dairy goats and kids on the Mexican plateau. *Arq. Bras. Med. Vet. Zootec*. 57, 77-84.
 62. Roche, J.R., Friggens, N.C., Kay, J.K., Fisher, M.W., Stafford, K.J., Berry, D.P., 2009. Invited review: Body condition score and its association with dairy cow productivity, health, and welfare. *Journal of Dairy Science*,

- 92, 5769-5801.
63. Rotruck, J.T., Pope, A.L., Ganther, H.E., Hafeman, D.G., Hoekstra, W.G., 1973. Selenium: Biochemical role as a component of glutathione peroxidase. *Science*, 179, 588-590.
 64. Segerson, E.C., Ganapathy, S.N., 1980. Fertilization of ova in selenium/vitamin E treated ewes maintained on two planes of nutrition. *J. Anim. Sci.* 51, 386-394.
 65. Schomburg, L., Riese, C., Michaelis, M., Griebert, E., Klein, M., Sapin, R., Schweizer, U., Köhrle, J., 2007. Synthesis and metabolism of thyroid hormones is preferentially maintained in selenium-deficient transgenic mice. *Endocrinology*, 147, 1306-1313.
 66. Sharma, N., Singh, N.K., Singh, O.P., Pandey, V., Verma, P.K., 2011. Oxidative Stress and Antioxidant Status during Transition Period in Dairy Cows. *Asian-Aust. Journal of Animal Science*, 24 (4), 479-484.
 67. Sheppard, A.D., Blom, L., Grant, A.B., 1984. Levels of selenium in blood and tissues associated with some selenium deficiency diseases in New Zealand sheep. *N.Z. Vet. J.* 32, 91-95.
 68. Skřivan, M., Englmaierová, M., Marounek, M., Skřivanová, V., Taubner, T., Vít, T., 2016. Effect of dietary magnesium, calcium, phosphorus, and limestone grain size on productive performance and eggshell quality of hens. *Czech J. Anim. Science*, 61(10), 473-480.
 69. Sordillo, L.M., 2005. Factors affecting mammary gland immunity mastitis susceptibility. *Livestock Prod. Sci.*, 98: 89-99.
 70. Sordillo, L.M., Aitken, S.L., 2009. Impact of oxidative stress on the health and immune function of dairy cattle. *Veterinary Immunology and Immunopathology*, 128, 104-109.
 71. Sordillo, L.M., 2011. New Concepts in the Causes and Control of Mastitis. *Mammary Gland Biol. Neoplasia*, 16, 271-273.
 72. Spears, W.J., Harvey, R.W., Segerson, E.C., 1986. Effects of marginal selenium deficiency and winter protein supplementation on growth, reproduction and selenium status of beef cattle. *J. Anim. Science*, 63, 586-593.
 73. Spears, J.W., Weiss, W.P., 2008. Role of antioxidants and trace elements in health and immunity of transition dairy cows. *Veterinary Journal*, 176, 70-76.
 74. Stadtman, T.C., 2005. Selenoproteins - tracing the role of trace element in protein function. *PLoS Biology*, 3, 2077.
 75. Suttle, N.F., and Jones, D.G., 1989. Recent developments in trace element metabolism and functions: Trace elements, disease resistance and immune responsiveness in ruminants. *J. Nutrition*, 119, 1055-1061.
 76. Tillard, E., Humblot, P., Faye, B., Lecomte, P., Dohoo, I, Bocquier, F., 2008. Post-calving factors affecting conception risk in Holstein dairy cows in tropical and sub-tropical conditions. *Theriogenology*, 69(4), 443-457.
 77. Tomas, F.M., and Potter, B.J., 1976. The site of magnesium absorption from the ruminant stomach. *Br. J. Nutrition*, 36, 37.
 78. Tyler, J.W., Casteel, S., Larson, R.L, Tessman, R.K, Randle, R., Miller, R.B., and Holle, J., 2003. Selenium status of spring-born feeder calves. *Int. J. Applied Res. Vet. Medicine*, 1(1).
 79. Underwood, E. J., and Suttle, N. F., 1999. The mineral nutrition of livestock. Moredun Research Institute, Pentlands Science Park, UK.
 80. Underwood, E.J., and Suttle, N.F., 2010. The mineral nutrition of livestock (4th edition). CABI Publishing, Wallingford, UK.
 81. Whanger, P.D., 2002. Seleno-compounds in plants and animals and their biological significance. *J. Am. Coll. Nutrition*, 21, 223-232.
 82. Xia, Y., Hill, K.E., Byrne, D.W., Xu, J., Burk, R.F., 2005. Effectiveness of selenium supplements in a low-selenium area of China. *Am. J. Clin. Nutrition*, 81, 829-834.
 83. Zywił, M.G., Cherian, J.J., Banerjee, S., Cheung, A.C., Wong, F., Butany, J., Gilbert, C., Overgaard, C., Syed, K., Jacobs, J.J., Mont, M.A., 2016. Systemic cobalt toxicity from total hip arthroplasties: review of a rare condition Part 2. measurement, risk factors, and step-wise approach to treatment. *The bone & joint journal*. 98(1), 14-20.